

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Space Court Foundation. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

GOVERNING ART IN OUTER SPACE

MARIA BORISLAVOVA POPOVA¹

ABSTRACT

Art has always been a means for humanity to find common grounds for communication, joy, and even peace. As space innovation has emerged, artists have found ways to diversify their work and expand their capabilities, sharing their ideas in space. They started sending artworks into outer space, which led to the occurring opportunity to consider supporting those creators through legal and ethical frameworks for space-based art.

The main benefits for the artist from those regulations would be licensing, copyright protections, and intellectual property rights. This could help establish originality, secure funding, and stimulate global recognition. Space-based artworks, however, and especially those launched by private entities, raise significant jurisdictional questions. Issues regarding national laws should be addressed. It should matter whether the artwork is under State protection or is a private initiative. Without legal clarity, disputes over ownership, liability, and cultural representation may arise.

Furthermore, artworks in orbit risk disrupting the space environment by contributing to light and noise pollution or generating debris, undermining the principles of the Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies. The Treaty establishes principles of peaceful use, non-appropriation, and shared benefit. As space becomes increasingly commercialised, artistic projects may be treated differently from commercial advertising or satellite infrastructure. Moreover, space art may also serve as a form of cultural diplomacy as it may be a symbolic gesture of peace and unity.

This article argues for the development of legal instruments that encourage sustainable and peaceful artistic activity in space.

KEYWORDS: Space, Art Innovations, Copyright, Environment, Diplomacy.

¹ Faculty of Law, Sofia University 'St. Kliment Ohridski', Sofia, Bulgaria; popova.mariya113@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Outer space was historically perceived as a primarily scientific domain,² where States pursued technological advancement and the collection of data on celestial bodies.³ However, much of this activity was also closely tied to geopolitical interests, as national programs often operated under the guise of science while advancing military and strategic capabilities.⁴ Although the placement of weapons of mass destruction in orbit and the use of celestial bodies for hostile military purposes were prohibited, the presence of military personnel in space, who historically comprised the majority of astronauts and cosmonauts, was not restricted.⁵

Over time, the focus of outer space has expanded beyond scientific exploration and geopolitical competition.⁶ Outer space has evolved into space for artistic expression.⁷ Artists have grown an interest in technology and exploration of territories beyond Earth's atmosphere.⁸ They have collaborated with entities which launch space objects and have even finished projects on painted rockets, orbital sculptures, space museums, and satellite-borne digital artworks. Those efforts often symbolise the never-ending aspirations of humanity to learn and explore, as well as the capabilities of human nature.⁹ It only shows how close the fields of science and art are related.

As art leaves the Earth's borders, new questions are posed before the legal sphere. Importance needs to be drawn to the distinction between commerciality and the pure willingness of people to expand their field of creativity,¹⁰ on the one hand, and, on the other, to connect with each other based on that creative expression, especially on an intercultural level.¹¹ The prerequisites of those aspects are different as they serve a slightly different purpose from one another. It should be theorised about the morality of creating just for the sake of it on the plain of personal interest, parallel to the benefits to all humankind.

The existing body of space law is not designed to accommodate cultural activities, regardless of their objectives. Though there is some progress, e.g. the One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space (OSS2PHH) Act in the US, it is merely a recommendation and not a policy act, which has not

² Pyne, S. J. (2006). *Seeking newer worlds: An historical context for space exploration* (Chapter 1). In S. J. Dick & R. D. Launius (Eds.), *Critical issues in the history of spaceflight* (7). NASA History Division. <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/sp-4702.pdf>.

³ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl (Eds.), Popova & Reynders (Asst. Eds.), & Volynskaya, Katsura-Trumpel, & Ladeyshchikov (Trans.). (2017). *Cologne Commentary on Space Law* (14). BWV. BERLINER WISSENSCHAFTS-VERLAG.

⁴ Farooqui, M. O., & Qureshi, T. (2024). Outer space militarization and the emerging paradigm of weaponization: Implications for space security and international regulation. *Revista Justiça do Direito*, 38(2), 116–145. <https://doi.org/10.5335/rjd.v38i2.15311>.

⁵ Gres, T., et al. (2022). *Astronaut profile evolution through time and space: Study of the past, current and future requirements*.

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Tania-Gres/publication/364351942_Astronaut_profile_evolution_through_time_and_space_Study_of_the_past_current_and_future_requirements/links/634e67296e0d367d91a7390d/Astronaut-profile-evolution-through-time-and-space-Study-of-the-past-current-and-future-requirements.pdf.

⁶ Triscott, N. (2016). *Critical art and outer space: A curatorial inquiry into space as a global commons* [Conference paper]. Westminster Research.

https://westminsterresearch.westminster.ac.uk/download/cbb3f32394f4bcf305f83908d30388f5f89d7645926b4a2e51753b5ee2ead3ce/180168/CriticalArtandOuterSpace_Triscott.pdf (westminsterresearch.westminster.ac.uk).

⁷ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl, *supra* note 3.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Dissanayake, E. (2010). *Why we make art: And why it is taught* (2nd ed.) (p. 5). Intellect / Chicago University Press.

https://books.google.bg/books?hl=en&lr=&id=DvmACgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=why+we+create+art&ots=9LquHwLS-g&sig=Uh6e3hubsrsmdBgj86uWqagqB1g&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=why%20we%20create%20art&f=false.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ *Ibid.*

yet been applied by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA).¹² International treaties primarily focus on fundamental aspects of space policy, including scientific advancement, security, safety, and liability.¹³ While some national laws address issues such as intellectual property, taxation, or even voting rights for space-based activities, there is no comprehensive legal framework specifically tailored to regulate cultural initiatives in space.¹⁴ As a result, space art exists in a regulatory gap, raising questions about authorization, jurisdiction, environmental impact, and the protection of creators' rights that current instruments do not explicitly address.¹⁵ The methodology of exploring space should be altered in order to meet the needs of the emerging focus on art.¹⁶ The regulations should leave space for the cultural development, irrespective of the purpose – either commercial, or universal and non-profitable.¹⁷ Alongside that necessity, another question is debated – how to govern the art field in the space context. The duality of the problem lies in the debate over whether art should be governed as a collective good or as a private enterprise.¹⁸ The advantages of both should be discussed, as well as their downsides for both artists and the public.

2. METHODOLOGY

This article adopts a doctrinal methodology, combining legal analysis and theoretical reflection. Its aim is to explore the question of whether artistic expression should be subject to legal regulation in the context of sending artworks into outer space for various reasons.

It includes an analysis of the legal space instruments, such as sources of law and subsidiary materials, to identify any possible protection of cultural activities in relation to the space field, considering environmental protection.

The article proposes policy and legal recommendations to align artistic expression in outer space. It adopts a cultural-commons perspective, arguing that outer space should be understood as a scientific frontier and simultaneously, as a shared aesthetic and diplomatic domain.

3. THE EMERGENCE OF ART IN OUTER SPACE

3.1. Historical overview

The philosophical and legal dilemmas around artistic activities in outer space are not merely theoretical. Artists have already begun the exploration of space art in the twentieth century. Examples of early space artworks are the Moon Museum¹⁹ in 1969 and the Voyager Golden Record²⁰ in 1977. They both carry the heritage of human civilisation into interstellar space and depict the striving of

¹² One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act, Pub. L. No. 116-275, 134 Stat. 3358 (2020).

¹³ United Nations. (1967). Article I. *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies* (Outer Space Treaty). https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_21_2220E.pdf.

¹⁴ Vafai, N. (2023, November 15). Celestial art law: An exploration of the artistic landscape and laws governing art in space. Center for Art Law. <https://itsartlaw.org/2023/11/15/celestial-art-law-an-exploration-of-the-artistic-landscape-and-laws-governing-art-in-space/>.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Triscott, *supra* note 6 at 5.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Rendell, J. (2000). Public art: Between public and private. In *Locality, regeneration & divers[c]ities* (p. 21). <http://ndl.ethernet.edu.et/bitstream/123456789/44947/1/167.pdf#page=20>.

¹⁹ Guridi, R. (2019). A museum on the moon? *The Moon Museum, exhibition space off limits*. *Revista de Arquitectura*, 21. https://www.proquest.com/openview/fdedc429df0bc2f54975c92cd7f9160b/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=1216382&casa_token=Xj_8nu6AmBYAAAAA:LPJCySuweIEwCL2tOFXDfaJHSanIRfOMItk5EjwAjjKdgM7IF6-KC_NsjrEvK6QGdYl4OSNKBdqA.

²⁰ Robinson, Z. (2022, January 23). *Diplomacy with aliens: The story of the Voyager Golden Records*. <https://zsrobinson.com/posts/diplomacy-with-aliens/>.

humanity for peace, identity, and human capabilities. Despite their objects being different, the Moon Museum showcases the works of six American artists on a tiny ceramic chip,²¹ while the Golden Record is a display of the sounds and images of our civilisation;²² they both illustrate the growing involvement of artists in space activities and the necessity for regulation of the field of space art.

Another aspect of the influence of space art is its relation to nationalistic urges and State propaganda.²³ During the Cold War, space imagery and artistic renderings were not merely neutral expressions of human aspiration; they were potent tools used by both the United States and the Soviet Union to signal technological superiority and cultural dominance.²⁴ For instance, the Soviet Union commissioned posters, stamps, and large-scale public art celebrating Sputnik and Yuri Gagarin's flights, portraying space exploration as proof of socialist scientific and ideological supremacy.²⁵ Similarly, the United States leveraged imagery of the Apollo missions, including iconic photographs such as the 'Earthrise' from Apollo 8, in combination with media campaigns and commemorative art, to convey American technological prowess and leadership in space.²⁶ This historical context complicates the notion of space art as a purely non-political diplomatic endeavour. Even contemporary projects launched via national agencies risk being perceived as soft-power instruments designed to support national prestige rather than foster universal unity. Acknowledging this legacy is vital for any modern regulatory framework that seeks to distinguish between state-sponsored messaging and independent creative expression.

3.2. Contemporary development

More recent art projects incorporate technology, demonstrating that artistic creativity can be closely connected to scientific progress. They encompass a modern take on artistic means through the creation of, for instance, orbital light installations,²⁷ satellite-based digital art, and even blockchain certification of the art via space NFTs. Tavares Strachan is an example of an artist whose work investigates science, technology, and history.²⁸ His practice draws upon the conceptual frameworks of aeronautical and astronomical science, deep-sea exploration, and extreme climatology to produce allegories that examine cultural displacement and human aspirations. The ENOCH project demonstrates Strachan's engagement with these themes, most notably through his collaboration with SpaceX to launch the artwork aboard one of the company's spacecraft.²⁹ ENOCH is expected to burn up in the atmosphere in December 2025, as the name refers to a biblical figure who is able to enter the afterlife according to the story.³⁰

Strachan is not without precedent in the twenty-first century. Many other artists have his aspirations to create a work, which is enriched with symbolism and leaves a message to humanity about their understanding of the world, while also demonstrating the capabilities of contemporary society and reflecting on the technological achievements of our civilisation.³¹ For instance, the Mayak satellite

²¹ Guridi, *supra* note 19 at 245.

²² Robinson *supra* note 20.

²³ Kallen, S. (2019). Nationalism, ideology, and the Cold War Space Race. *Constellations*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.29173/cons29377> (p. 6); Conversi, D. (2009). Art, nationalism and war: Political futurism in Italy (1909–1944). *Nations and Nationalism*, 15(1), 92–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2008.00185.x>.

²⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵ Banerjee, A. (2013). Between Sputnik and Gagarin. *Space Flight, Children's Periodicals, and the Circle of Imagination*. In M. Balina & L. Rudova (Eds.), *Russian children's literature and culture* (p. 68). Routledge.

²⁶ Keltner, K. A. (2007). *From myth to metaphor to memory: A rhetorical analysis of televised representations of Project Apollo, 1968–2004* (Doctoral dissertation, Ohio University). ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (Publication No. 3280032).

²⁷ Yalcinkaya, G. (2019, March 22). *Trevor Paglen's art installation in limbo in Earth's orbit*. *dezeen*. <https://www.dezeen.com/2019/03/22/orbital-reflector-trevor-paglen-design/>.

²⁸ Strachan, T. (n.d.). *Artist profile*. Galerie Perrotin. https://www.perrotin.com/artists/tavares_strachan/797#videos.

²⁹ Strachan, T. (2015–17). *ENOCH (display unit)* [Sculpture]. The Metropolitan Museum of Art. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/856524>.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ *Ibid.*

project in 2017 launched a reflective structure designed to unfold in space and shine brightly in the night sky, transforming a satellite into a visible artistic object for observers on Earth.³² In addition to the symbolic nature of the project, it exposes the importance of scientific value in such undertakings. The significance lies not only in the necessity to draw attention to space research and activities, but also in the contribution to the problem-solving in areas such as the apparent stellar magnitude of space objects.³³

Similarly, Rocket Lab's 'Humanity Star' satellite was conceived as a symbolic mirror-like sphere intended to orbit the planet as a reminder of humanity's shared presence in space.³⁴ Another example is Trevor Paglen's 'Orbital Reflector', developed with the Nevada Museum of Art, which placed a reflective sculptural satellite into orbit to function as a temporary celestial monument visible from Earth.³⁵ Even though not all of the projects demonstrate a direct link between science and aesthetics, they become a blueprint of how artists increasingly collaborate with aerospace engineers and private space companies to transform orbit into a new exhibition space.

4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF SPACE LAW IN ART CONTEXT

4.1. Deficiency of the legal framework of art

As the importance of space art has now been clarified, it is vital for artists, scientists, and even States to picture its place within the legal system.

Existing space law was not originally designed to accommodate artistic and cultural activities. Perhaps, it was not anticipated to play a role in the development of the world, as historically, the focus of space legislation has been on the scientific and technological space evolution,³⁶ rather than creative or recreational endeavours in outer space. It was necessary to first understand the basics of the space possibilities, and only then, room for secondary activities may have been left. The *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty; OST)³⁷ primarily established principles for the peaceful use of outer space, liability, and resource ownership, without considering the unique challenges posed by art projects in space. The reason behind it is enshrined in the historical context as the negotiation process of the treaty was materializing the final draft in an era dominated by State actors and Cold War imperatives.³⁸ No State currently has a specific, standalone 'Space Art Act' or comprehensive legislation dedicated solely to artistic and cultural pursuits in outer space.

4.2. Existing regulations

All international instruments reflect this historical line. Those instruments highlight the principles, aiming to preserve safety and protect stability between States. The main focuses of the Outer Space Treaty are to avoid militarization of outer space, prevent national appropriation of any celestial bodies, ensure State responsibility and liability, respectively for any breaches and damages, and to promote peaceful exploration of space. Those goals are reaffirmed in the subsequent treaties and conventions (i.e. the *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return*

³² Cosmo Mayak. (2017). *Mayak satellite – The Mayak satellite is the brightest star in the night sky*. Retrieved from <https://www.cosmomayak.com/>.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Rocket Lab Reveals "The Humanity Star," a "Disco Ball" Satellite Shining From Space. (2018). Space.com. Retrieved from <https://www.space.com/39482-rocket-lab-reveals-humanity-star-satellite.html>.

³⁵ Paglen, T. (2018, November 25). *Orbital Reflector: The artist firing a satellite into space*. The Guardian. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2018/nov/25/orbital-reflector-trevor-paglen-satellite>.

³⁶ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl, *supra* note 3 at 110.

³⁷ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies. (1967, January 27). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

³⁸ Collis, J. (2009). *The geostationary orbit: A critical legal geography of space's most valuable real estate*. In D. Bell & M. Parker (Eds.), *Space travel and culture: From Apollo to space tourism* (p. 47). Routledge.

of Objects Launched into Outer Space (ARRA),³⁹ the Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects (Liability Convention; LIAB),⁴⁰ the Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space (Registration Convention; REG),⁴¹ and the Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (MOON), although the latter has only been ratified by 17 States).⁴² The outer space area is also governed by multiple customary rules, existing in national laws and international practice;⁴³ however, there is also no mention of the new role of private actors in the art field. At a national level, States with advanced space sectors have their own regulatory regimes. In the Russian Federation, e.g., space activities are governed by the *Law on Space Activities* (No. 5663-1 of 1993), which sets out general principles, licensing requirements for the manufacture, testing, launch, and control of space objects, and certification regimes for space technology, all aimed at scientific, national-economic, and security goals.⁴⁴ Supplementary normative acts, such as the statute on licensing procedures and government resolutions that define the mandate of Roscosmos, implement these requirements and make clear that any actor planning to conduct space operations under Russian jurisdiction must be licensed and compliant with State oversight.⁴⁵

Because neither the existing international treaties nor most national frameworks were drafted with artistic or cultural projects in mind, they leave ambiguities when such projects are proposed – whether concerning licensing, responsibility for orbital debris, or how creative content in space should be regulated.⁴⁶ For example, even a satellite launched for aesthetic purposes must typically navigate the same licensing and registration requirements as a scientific spacecraft, despite no harmful intent or traditional space use.

4.3. New necessities

Even though art, as a space activity, is still relatively rare, its rise is inevitable in the near future.⁴⁷ Therefore, new regulations need to emerge to protect the human values embodied in such creations. Law should be a pre-emptive governance tool, which, based on the existing precedents,⁴⁸ ensures the legal certainty with regard to the protection of intellectual property and financial benefits of artists, on the one hand, but also the protection of the space environment, human rights, and scientific research, on the other. In practice, this dual function means that law would establish clear guidelines on what

³⁹ Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space. (1968, April 22). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/rescueagreement.html>.

⁴⁰ Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects. (1972, March 29). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/liability-convention.html>.

⁴¹ Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space. (1975, January 14). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/registration-convention.html>.

⁴² Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies. (1979, December 18). United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/moon-agreement.html>.

⁴³ Vereshchetin, V. S., & Danilenko, G. M. (1994). Custom as a source of international law of outer space. Routledge.

⁴⁴ Law on Space Activities, No. 5663-1 (Russ.) of 20 August 1993. On Space Activities. Retrieved from <https://legalacts.ru/doc/zakon-rf-ot-20081993-n-5663-1-o/>.

⁴⁵ Federal Law No. 19-FZ (Russ.) of 2 February 2006, as amended up to Federal Law No. 216-FZ of 13 July 2015. *On Amendments to Certain Laws and the Repeal of Certain Provisions of Certain Laws of the Russian Federation in Connection with the Adoption of the Federal Law on the Placement of Orders for the Supply of Goods, Performance of Work, and Provision of Services for State and Municipal Needs*.

⁴⁶ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

⁴⁷ Wang, F. Y., & Zhai, C. (2026). The evolution of space art: Dream, Monolith and Revelation. *Acta Astronautica*, 238(Part A) (p. 908). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.09.049>.

⁴⁸ Stockdale, L. P. D. (2013). *Governing the future, mastering time: Temporality, sovereignty, and the pre-emptive politics of (in)security* (Doctoral dissertation, McMaster University). McMaster University Institutional Repository. <https://prod-ms-be.lib.mcmaster.ca/server/api/core/bitstreams/aeac37f6-fe83-4c34-a2da-ea47be0c4d3f/content>.

types of artistic activities are permissible, require authorization and supervision for space-based projects, and set technical and ethical standards for materials, reflectivity, or orbital behaviour. By combining protective and regulatory measures, law can both empower artistic expression and ensure that the human values underlying space art are aligned with the collective, long-term interests of the global community.

The fact that there is no single legal regime specifically designed for artistic activities in outer space does not mean that such projects exist outside regulation. They are situated at the intersection of two already highly regulated fields: *space activities*⁴⁹ and *artistic or cultural production*.⁵⁰ International space law instruments, such as the Outer Space Treaty, the Liability Convention, and the Registration Convention, establish obligations relating to State responsibility, liability, and the registration of space objects. At the same time, artistic creation and cultural heritage are governed by separate national and international frameworks, including cultural property laws, intellectual property regimes, and conventions such as the UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions.⁵¹ The difficulty arises because these two regulatory spheres were developed independently and pursue different objectives: space law prioritizes safety, liability, and the sustainable use of the orbital environment, whereas cultural and art-related legislation focuses on creativity, cultural expression, and heritage protection. As a result, projects that place artworks in orbit or otherwise use space as a medium often fall between regulatory categories.⁵² Authorities may struggle to determine which rules should apply, how artistic intent should be assessed within technical licensing frameworks, or how cultural value should be weighed against operational or environmental concerns.⁵³ This fragmentation can create practical difficulties in implementation and may also leave legal *lacunae*, where neither body of law provides clear guidance for the governance of artistic activities conducted in outer space.⁵⁴

There are two main possible approaches to achieve the goal of filling the legal gap in the regulation. The first one involves incorporating targeted amendments or interpretative guidelines into the already existing sources⁵⁵ of law, including space law as part of public international law. An instance could be by clarifying within the Outer Space Treaty⁵⁶ or through implementing guidelines adopted by international bodies⁵⁷ that artistic and cultural projects constitute a legitimate form of ‘use of outer space’, provided that they comply with existing obligations regarding authorization, supervision, and environmental protection. In practice, such an approach could require States to explicitly include cultural or artistic missions within their national licensing frameworks for space activities, ensuring that projects initiated by artists or cultural institutions are subject to the same authorization and supervision requirements that apply to other non-governmental space activities under Article VI of the OST.

⁴⁹ Santos, E. A. (2025, July 4). *International law and the regulation of outer space*. Diplomacy & Law. <https://www.diplomacyandlaw.com/post/international-law-and-the-regulation-of-outer-space>.

⁵⁰ UNESCO. (2023). *Artistic freedom: International standards and challenges* (UNESCO Creativity Policy Series). UNESCO. https://www.unesco.org/creativity/sites/default/files/medias/fichiers/2023/01/artistic_freedom_pdf_web.pdf.

⁵¹ UNESCO. (2005). *Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions* (adopted 20 October 2005; entered into force 18 March 2007). <https://legal.un.org/avl/ha/cppdce/cppdce.html>

⁵² Brobst, J. A. (2024). *Legal strategies to preserve the natural and cultural heritage of space*. In S. Bhat B. (Ed.), *Space tourism: Legal and policy aspects* (pp. 133–152). Routledge India.

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

⁵⁵ Azaria, D. (2020). ‘Codification by interpretation’: The International Law Commission as an interpreter of international law. *European Journal of International Law*, 31(1), 171–200. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/cha016>.

⁵⁶ UNOOSA. (2025, May 5). *Clarifying ambiguities in the Outer Space Treaty: Conference room paper by Space Renaissance International* (A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.17). https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac.105c.22025crp/aac.105c.22025crp.17_0.htm

⁵⁷ Azaria, *supra* note 55.

The second approach concerns the adoption of a new regulatory instrument,⁵⁸ specifically addressing artistic and cultural activities in outer space. Such an instrument could take the form of either a *binding* international agreement⁵⁹ or a *non-binding* soft-law framework.⁶⁰ A binding treaty would provide clear and enforceable obligations for States regarding the authorization, supervision, and protection of space-based artworks, as well as rules on liability, environmental responsibility, and the preservation of culturally significant space objects.⁶¹ Alternatively, a non-binding instrument, such as international guidelines, principles, or recommendations adopted within forums like the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), could offer a more flexible and politically feasible solution.⁶² Such soft-law mechanisms could establish the best practices for licensing artistic missions and promote standards which ensure that artistic projects do not interfere with scientific missions or contribute to orbital debris. Such techniques may encourage States to integrate cultural considerations into national space legislation.

Irrespective of the approach the international community chooses, new legislation would be beneficial to expand the human reach in outer space, as it is already not merely a scientific frontier, but also a creative commons. In this regard, future regulation could draw inspiration from international frameworks developed for the protection of cultural heritage, such as the UNESCO Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage and adapt some of their governance mechanisms to the space domain. For example, the UNESCO Convention principles can be incorporated into space law by treating outer space as a ‘shared aesthetic and diplomatic domain’ similar to how Earth-bound heritage sites are protected. International law could adopt the UNESCO view that certain cultural achievements belong to all humankind. This aligns with Article I OST, which defines space as the ‘province of all mankind’. Furthermore, UNESCO’s focus on ‘natural heritage’ as defined in Article 2 of the Convention can be used to bolster space law’s environmental protection, specifically regarding the mitigation of orbital debris and ‘light and noise pollution’ caused by artistic installations. Additionally, States can incorporate the principles under the Convention into their domestic authorization and supervision process as required under Article VI of the OST. For instance, national regulators could require artists and private companies to prove that their space-based art complies with ethical and environmental standards similar to those used for protected sites on Earth.

5. SECTION ART AS MEANS IN DIPLOMACY FOR INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AND DIALOGUE

5.1. Advantages of cultural diplomacy

Few artists set out with the explicit goal of contributing to diplomacy; indeed, art often challenges authority and questions commonly accepted norms.⁶³ Yet one of the enduring advantages of art is its potential to serve as a vehicle for diplomacy.⁶⁴ There are several types of diplomacy, with the political one being the main field. However, subsidiary to its relevance is also the cultural diplomacy. Cultural

⁵⁸ Asatryan, A. (2023). The concept of filling, eliminating gaps in law and ways to overcome them. *Byurakan Young Scientists’ Journal*, 14(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.46991/BYSU:C/2023.14.1.003>.

⁵⁹ Azaria, *supra* note 55.

⁶⁰ Waibel, M. (2024, September 18). *Potential indirect legal effects of non-legally binding instruments* (Panel 2 statement, Second Practitioners’ Workshop on Non-Legally Binding Instruments in International Law, Vienna, Austria). Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/panel-2-statement-m-waibel-final/1680b1f73d>.

⁶¹ Azaria, *supra* note 55.

⁶² Waibel, *supra* note 60.

⁶³ Adeleke, K. (2025, August 25). *How art challenges social norms: A bold history of creative disruption*. ARTCENTRON. <https://artcentron.com/2025/08/25/how-art-challenges-social-norms/>.

⁶⁴ Tibererwa, E. (2025). *Cultural diplomacy: Art as a tool for international relations*. *Eurasian Experiment Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 92–102. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390696010_Cultural_Diplomacy_Art_as_a_Tool_for_International_Relations.

diplomacy is grounded in two preconditions.⁶⁵ Firstly, mutual respect and understanding between actors and, secondly, the understanding of culture as a combination of art, language and education.⁶⁶ Those areas lead to some of the most effective human exchanges, as they are meant to overcome prejudice and disinformation.⁶⁷ An example in practice of cultural diplomacy is the loan by the Vatican to the Albert Museum in London. During a visit of the Pope in Great Britain, the Vatican lent 16th-century tapestries, illustrating scenes from the Acts of the Apostles. These invaluable artworks, seldom displayed outside the Vatican, convey another narrative about the Catholic Church, enriching its public image and fostering engagement through a medium which is less politically contentious.⁶⁸ Such examples once again show the importance of diplomacy through cultural means.

5.2. Cultural diplomacy in space

Space art can also serve the purpose of cultural diplomacy, as it generally represents another form of art. It could be a unifying symbol, transcending borders, which preconditions its potential for cultural exchange and global cooperation. Such an approach is coherent with the principles of Article III of the OST regarding the obligation for international cooperation and understanding. It may be used in the peacekeeping process through collaborative international art. States can initiate collective projects to show their alacrity for international peace.

However, without appropriate coordination, this tool for soft diplomacy risks becoming a form of cultural dominance where only wealthy nations are able to send art since those projects are costly, both the materials for the artwork, which need to be altered in a way to be safe for launch, and the spacecrafts.⁶⁹ Proper coordination is required in order for any political messages to be avoided.⁷⁰ Political influence is contrary to the goals of cultural diplomacy, which encourages mutual understanding among actors.⁷¹

The new space art framework should ensure equitable cultural access to any Party. Space should remain canvas for all humanity and not be limited to the privileged few. States should effectively coordinate among themselves in such a way that even the least developed countries, according to the United Nations,⁷² should have the opportunity to participate in world policymaking.⁷³ Each State should also have the obligation to foster creativity by allowing any artist to join the initiatives. They may include financial support practices in their legal frameworks in order to stimulate all artists to create the future of the international community.⁷⁴

In this context, a future space art framework could clarify procedural aspects, such as authorization mechanisms, criteria for international representation, and the registration status of artistic payloads.

⁶⁵ Goff, P. M. (2013). *Cultural diplomacy*. In A. F. Cooper, J. Heine, & R. Thakur (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of modern diplomacy* (420). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199588862.013.0024>.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ Ibid, 422.

⁶⁹ Watlington, E. (2023, May 16). *The best and worst artists of our time are sending their work into space*. ARTnews. <https://www.artnews.com/art-in-america/columns/space-art-jeff-koons-xu-bing-xin-liu-1234667481/>.

⁷⁰ Demirel, I. N., & Altıntaş, O. (2012). Relationship between art and politics. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 51, p. 446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.08.241>.

⁷¹ Tibererwa, E. (2025). *Cultural diplomacy: Art as a tool for international relations*. EURASIAN EXPERIMENT Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 7(1), (93). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/390696010_Cultural_Diplomacy_Art_as_a_Tool_for_International_Relations_researchgate.net+1.

⁷² United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. (n.d.). *UN list of least developed countries*. <https://unctad.org/topic/least-developed-countries/list>.

⁷³ Mabry, M. C., & Mabry, B. D. (1981). *The role of the arts in developing countries: Thailand, a case study*. *Ekistics*, 48(288), (248). https://www.jstor.org/stable/43620542_jstor.org+1.

⁷⁴ United Nations Human Rights Council. (2013). *Report of the Special Rapporteur in the field of cultural rights, Farida Shaheed: The right to freedom of artistic expression and creativity* (A/HRC/23/34). <https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/23/34>.

By aligning artistic initiatives with existing legal obligations under international space law, space art can develop as a legitimate form of cultural diplomacy without undermining the principles of responsibility, transparency, and cooperation that govern activities in outer space.

6. SPACE COMMERCIALIZATION

6.1. Commercialization of space posing new challenges

Whether private initiatives for space art exist is no longer a matter for debate, as the answer is affirmative.⁷⁵ Numerous private companies now launch space objects and collaborate with artists, willing to develop the space art field. As aforementioned, there are already some cases of artists sending their works into space, both presently and historically, such as Tavares Strachan, Xu Bing,⁷⁶ Jeff Koons,⁷⁷ and also the early collaborative project Moon Museum.

Commercialization of space has gradually transformed the exclusive domain of national space agencies into a rapidly expanding frontier for private actors. Those actors include companies, artistic institutions, private sponsors, and individual artists. As access to outer space becomes increasingly feasible, questions arise on how to regulate private artistic initiatives in outer space.⁷⁸

From a regulatory perspective, private space activities are already governed by several foundational norms of international space law, which regulate both responsibility (e.g. the aforementioned in Article VI OST) and liability regimes. Liability considerations play a central role in regulating private initiatives. The Liability Convention establishes that launching States are internationally liable for damage caused by their space objects. Consequently, if an artwork forms part of a spacecraft payload or constitutes an independent object placed in orbit, the launching State may incur liability in the event of damage to other space objects, the space environment, or property on Earth. This legal framework incentivizes States to adopt strict authorization procedures and technical requirements for private launches, including those involving artistic payloads.

Another relevant regulatory aspect concerns planetary protection.⁷⁹ While many artistic projects are intended for orbit or symbolic missions, some initiatives have proposed sending artworks to the Moon or other celestial bodies. Such activities must comply with broader international obligations aimed at preventing harmful contamination of outer space environments. Article IX OST requires States to conduct activities in outer space with due regard to the interests of other States and to avoid harmful contamination of celestial bodies. In practice, these principles are implemented through internationally recognized planetary protection standards developed by the Committee on Space Research.⁸⁰ Artistic missions directed toward celestial bodies would therefore need to comply with scientific contamination control requirements, even if their primary purpose is cultural rather than scientific.

Even if we accept that artworks sent into space should remain under the jurisdiction of that launching State, new regulations are still necessary in order to draw the limitations of the artists' involvement in the space sector. Taken together, these legal and normative mechanisms demonstrate that private artistic initiatives in space must operate within the broader framework governing space activities. By

⁷⁵ Watlington, *supra* note 69.

⁷⁶ Xu Bing. (n.d.). *Project #707*. <https://www.xubing.com/en/work/details/707?type=project>.

⁷⁷ Rabb, M. (2024, February 16). Jeff Koons sculptures launched on a SpaceX mission to the moon. <https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-jeff-koons-sculptures-launched-spacex-mission-moon>.

⁷⁸ Amruta, G. K. S. (2025). *The role of private entities in outer space activities*. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 7(2), Article 41334. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2025.v07i02.41334>.

⁷⁹ Coustenis, A., et. al. (2023). Planetary protection: Updates and challenges for a sustainable space exploration. *Acta Astronautica*, 210, 446–452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.02.035>.

⁸⁰ Ehrenfreund, P., et. al. (2026, January). *Editorial to the 2026 version of the COSPAR Policy on Planetary Protection* (Space Research Today No. 224, pp. 15–16). COSPAR. https://cosparhq.cnes.fr/assets/uploads/2026/01/SRT_224_Editorial_PPP-Nov-2025.pdf.

integrating artistic missions into existing regimes of authorization, liability, environmental protection, and international cooperation, States can promote cultural expression in outer space, while also ensuring that such activities remain consistent with the principles of sustainability and peaceful use. In this way, space art can develop not merely as an individual creative endeavour but as a structured instrument of cultural diplomacy capable of fostering inclusive participation in humanity's shared space future.

6.2. *Legal aspects of space artworks – current and new regulations*

The increasing congestion of the low Earth orbit (LEO) represents one of the most pressing challenges in contemporary space governance. The proliferation of commercial satellites and other privately operated space objects has intensified concerns regarding orbital crowding and the sustainability of space activities.⁸¹ In this context, the question arises whether new types of objects fall within the existing definition of a 'space object'. Article I(d) LIAB defines a 'space object' as including component parts of a space object as well as its launch vehicle and parts thereof. Although this definition is intentionally broad, many objects may fall out of the scope of any of the instruments. Such ambiguities may arise when dealing with unconventional payloads, such as artworks sent into orbit independently or attached to a spacecraft's structures.

Such ambiguity may generate jurisdictional and accountability concerns. If certain artistic objects were interpreted as falling outside the existing legal definition of a space object, they could potentially escape the established frameworks of responsibility and liability under international space law. In such a scenario, no State would bear the obligations arising from activities conducted in outer space, thereby undermining the fundamental principle of State responsibility established in Article VI OST. For this reason, clarification regarding the legal classification of artistic payloads may be necessary to ensure that all activities conducted in space remain attributable to a launching State and therefore subject to international obligations.⁸²

The term 'space art' is currently only a doctrinal one. It is defined as a genre of art, which encompasses two distinct concepts.⁸³ The first one refers to the visual depiction of the universe through various artistic styles, such as paintings or digital works depicting the cosmos. The second one indicates that artworks are sent into space.⁸⁴

The artworks in space can remain in orbit indefinitely if effective measures for its de-orbit are not implemented.⁸⁵ This is an issue since those objects may become new long-term space debris. For this reason, the principles of OST should be fulfilled, and any new legislation could further deepen the measures for a solution. In this sense, the new regulations may appear to be *lex specialis* to the existing instruments.

However, addressing these challenges does not necessarily require entirely new binding legislation. While the development of specific legal instruments may eventually become necessary, significant regulatory progress can also be achieved through soft-law mechanisms, industry standards, and cooperative governance frameworks. The international space community relies on non-binding guidelines to address emerging challenges. For example, the Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines adopted by COPUOS and endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly encourage States and

⁸¹ Borowitz, M. (2018). Strategic implications of the proliferation of space situational awareness technology and information: Lessons learned from the remote sensing sector. *Space Policy*, 45, 123–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.05.002>.

⁸² World Intellectual Property Organization. (2004). *Intellectual property and space activities: Issue paper prepared by the International Bureau of WIPO* (OECD Contribution, para.47, p.12). Retrieved from https://www.wipo.int/documents/d/patents/docs-en-topics-outer-space-ip_space_wipo-contribution_oecd_2004.pdf.

⁸³ NASA. (2016, August 4). *NASA art program: The art of air and space*. NASA. <https://www.nasa.gov/art/nasa-art-program-the-art-of-air-and-space>.

⁸⁴ *Ibid.*

⁸⁵ Hobe, Schmidt-Tedd, & Schrogl, *supra* note 3 at 515.

private operators to design space missions in ways that reduce the creation of debris and ensure the long-term sustainability of orbital activities. Similar approaches could be extended to artistic missions through voluntary standards developed in collaboration with commercial launch providers, satellite operators, and cultural institutions.

New applications of the obligations of authorisation and supervision under Article VI OST should also be discussed. Measures regarding the tracking of the objects and their control of space art should be taken,⁸⁶ and the new framework should also include systems for de-orbit or in-space destruction if the piece is made from suitable, non-harming materials to the space environment.⁸⁷ Mechanisms for collision avoidance are also necessary in order for the work to fulfil its purpose and not to interfere with scientific objects,⁸⁸ especially since those mechanisms are still not fully developed in practice, and even the automated collision avoidance manoeuvres are undergoing improvements.

Additionally, the dark and quiet skies should be protected since the sun's reflections are a problem,⁸⁹ which is further magnified by the reflective spacecrafts.⁹⁰ Astronomers have raised growing concerns about the visual brightness and radio interference generated by large satellite constellations and other reflective spacecraft. These issues have been examined in international discussions on the protection of dark and quiet skies, which is an initiative supported by organizations such as the International Astronomical Union. The concept reflects a broader environmental perspective often described as 'space environmentalism', which emphasizes the need to protect both the orbital environment and the observational integrity of the night sky for scientific research and cultural heritage.⁹¹

Artistic space projects may unintentionally exacerbate these challenges. Several of the artistic initiatives mentioned earlier, such as the Mayak project and the Rocket Lab, involve highly reflective materials or symbolic objects designed to attract visual attention.⁹² The artists proudly present their projects as 'the brightest star in the night sky'. While such characteristics may serve artistic purposes, they can also increase light reflectivity in orbit, thereby contributing to optical interference with ground-based astronomical observations. If widely replicated, such projects could intensify existing concerns regarding orbital light pollution.⁹³

To mitigate these risks, several practical measures could be adopted within future governance frameworks for space art. First, authorization procedures under Article VI OST could require environmental impact assessments for artistic payloads, similar to those already implemented for certain scientific or commercial missions. Second, technical design standards could be introduced to limit reflectivity and reduce optical brightness, drawing on ongoing collaboration between satellite operators and astronomical institutions. Third, licensing authorities could require artistic objects placed in orbit to incorporate reliable end-of-life disposal mechanisms, including controlled de-orbiting within a specified timeframe. Finally, transparency mechanisms such as mandatory

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ Ibid, 505.

⁸⁸ Ibid, 181.

⁸⁹ Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. (2025, June 25–July 2). *Report of the Scientific and Technical Subcommittee on its sixty-second session: Conference room paper on dark and quiet skies for science and society* (Sixty-eighth session, Item 6 of the provisional agenda). United Nations. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/v25/047/48/pdf/v2504748.pdf>.

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ Marino, A., & Cheney, T. (2023). Centring environmentalism in space governance: Interrogating dominance and authority through a critical legal geography of outer space. *Space Policy*, 63, 101521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2022.101521>.

⁹² Lardies, G. (2025, July 9). *What is Rocket Lab launching into space and why are people angry about it?* The Spinoff. <https://thespinoff.co.nz/society/09-07-2025/what-is-rocket-lab-launching-into-space-and-why-are-people-angry-about-it>.

⁹³ Ibid.

registration and tracking could ensure that artistic payloads remain identifiable and manageable within existing space traffic coordination systems.

Ultimately, the emergence of space art reflects a broader transformation in the nature of space activities, as new actors and new forms of engagement enter the extraterrestrial domain. Rather than focusing exclusively on redefining the concept of a ‘space object’, future space governance frameworks should address the wider implications of these emerging activities. Binding legal obligations could be combined with soft-law instruments, technical standards, and collaborative governance mechanisms, which would lead the international community to be able to ensure that artistic expression in outer space develops in a manner consistent with the principles of sustainability, scientific protection, and the shared interests of humanity.

It is evident that balance should be sought to achieve optimal benefits for both the public interest, especially in the field of environmental protection and outer space scientific exploration, and private interest, which lies in the freedom of expression⁹⁴ and financial turnover,⁹⁵ and these two interests should be balanced.

7. BALANCE OF INTERESTS THROUGH LICENSING

7.1. *Why licensing is important*

When art is launched into outer space, it occupies a unique legal and ethical position. The creative expression is materialised in an existing object, which should fall into the jurisdiction of a specific State. If not regulated, it would belong to all humankind, which, although sounding altruistic, can cause problems to countries and artists.

Therefore, the principle of licensing in the field of intellectual property should be discussed to be applied by analogy in the international context of outer space. Depending on the goal of the project, a different type of Creative Commons (CC) license shall apply.⁹⁶

Regardless of the objective of the initiative, a minimum of protection should apply to artists. They need to be credited for their authorship of the artwork and need to have the right to control the use, reproduction, and modification of it. The current challenge is to protect the artist’s originality without diminishing the cultural value of international cooperation regarding outer space.⁹⁷

Creative Commons licensing allows creators to retain certain rights, while granting the public permission to use, share, or modify the artwork under specific conditions. They are beneficial to all Parties involved since they preserve the authorship of the artist whose works are publicly available.⁹⁸ On the other hand, they prevent monopolisation by private companies and individuals that might commercialise space art as exclusive intellectual property due to its specifics. This would promote collaboration between artists, companies and national space agencies.⁹⁹

7.2. *Types of CC licenses and their applications*

Depending on the purpose of the space art launch, two different types of launches may be defined: *commercial* and *non-commercial*. The commercial ones reflect the interest of the private entities,

⁹⁴ Dissanayake, *supra* note 9 at 10.

⁹⁵ Gupta, P. (2022). *If artists were given more opportunities, would they have a better chance at financial viability?* International Journal of Innovative Science & Research Technology, 7(12), p. 1404.

⁹⁶ Kim, M. (2008). *The Creative Commons and copyright protection in the digital era: Uses of Creative Commons licenses*. College of Communication, p. 192, doi:10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00392.x.

⁹⁷ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

⁹⁸ *Ibid*.

⁹⁹ *Ibid*, 202.

which may be related to extending human capabilities and financial turnover.¹⁰⁰ Non-commercial are the ones that safeguard scientific and diplomatic space exploration, hence are open to humanity.

Within this context, intellectual property rights become particularly relevant in determining how artworks sent into space may be reproduced, distributed, or commercially exploited. Copyright protection for artistic works is primarily governed by international agreements such as the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works and the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, which establish minimum standards for copyright protection among participating States. These frameworks grant creators exclusive rights over the reproduction, distribution, and adaptation of their works. However, artists may voluntarily grant broader permissions through standardized open licensing systems such as those developed by the Creative Commons (CC license).¹⁰¹

The licensing regarding commercial purposes is mainly of three types: attribution (CC BY), attribution-share-alike (CC BY-SA), and attribution-no-derivatives (CC BY-ND).¹⁰² The CC BY license allows users to copy, modify, distribute, and even sell the artwork, as long as they credit the author. They are useful to the artists in a way that the authors gain exposure and are more suitable for the creators to receive recognition. The CC BY-SA allow users to use or modify the work. Its best use is that it allows others to be inspired by the artwork. The last type is the CC BY-ND, which only permits usage, but not any modifications.¹⁰³

Licenses which prohibit commercial use are attribution-non-commercial (CC BY-NC), attribution-non-commercial-share-alike (CC BY-NC-SA), and attribution-non-commercial-no-derivatives (CC BY-NC-ND). The CC BY-NC allows users to copy and adapt the work for cultural or educational purposes only. The CC BY-NC-SA requires any derivative work to carry the same license, which prevents commercial exploitation. The CC BY-NC-ND is considered the most restrictive license as it only allows sharing with proper credit (i.e. is most suitable when the artwork is merely for display).¹⁰⁴

The potential application of such licensing systems to space art initiatives raises several practical considerations. For example, artists participating in missions that involve broadcasting images of artworks from orbit, reproducing digital models of space-based installations, or displaying artistic objects on spacecraft could license those works under specific Creative Commons frameworks. This would allow the public, scientific institutions, or educational organizations to reproduce and share images or digital representations of the artwork while respecting the rights of the original creator. Moreover, licensing agreements could be incorporated into launch contracts or collaborative mission agreements between artists, sponsors, and launch providers.

Jurisdictional considerations also play an important role in determining how intellectual property rights apply in outer space. Under Article VIII of the OST, a State retains jurisdiction and control over objects launched into outer space that are registered under its authority. Consequently, intellectual property disputes relating to artworks physically placed on spacecraft or orbital platforms may be governed by the domestic law of the launching State. This principle has already been applied in contexts such as the Agreement Concerning Cooperation on the Civil International Space Station, which establishes jurisdictional rules for intellectual property created aboard the International Space Station.¹⁰⁵

¹⁰⁰ Gupta, *supra* note 95 at 1405.

¹⁰¹ Margoni, T., & Peters, D. M. (n.d.). *Creative Commons licenses: Empowering open access*. University of Stirling. <https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/149666/1/149666.pdf>.

¹⁰² *Ibid.*

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ Agreement among the Government of Canada, Governments of Member States of the European Space Agency, the Government of Japan, the Government of the Russian Federation, and the Government of the United States of America concerning cooperation on the civil International Space Station. (1998, January 29).

In practice, a structured licensing framework for space art could therefore function as a complementary regulatory mechanism alongside existing space law obligations. By allowing artists to define how their works may be reproduced, adapted, or commercially used, Creative Commons licenses could facilitate cultural dissemination while preserving authors' rights.¹⁰⁶ At the same time, integrating such licensing systems into launch agreements and national authorization procedures would help ensure that space art projects operate within both intellectual property law and international space governance frameworks.¹⁰⁷ In this way, open licensing models could support the development of space art as a tool for cultural exchange while maintaining legal clarity regarding ownership, usage rights, and creative attribution.

8. CONCLUSION

To balance private interests with public welfare, States should adopt a spectrum of flexible soft-law instruments and national licensing procedures that support artists through copyright protection and facilitate launch access while enforcing technical standards for de-orbiting and reflectivity limits to ensure environmental sustainability. Such a framework would establish space art as a pivotal tool for cultural diplomacy in the 'province of all mankind', providing a neutral platform for symbolic unity and innovation unburdened by national appropriation. By adapting legislation to these emerging creative interests, the international community can provide a protective shield for peaceful exploration while maintaining the necessary restrictions to preserve the outer space environment for future generations.

International Space Station Intergovernmental Agreement. Retrieved from https://aerospace.org/sites/default/files/policy_archives/Space%20Station%20Intergovernmental%20Agreement%20Jan98.pdf.

¹⁰⁶ Vafai, *supra* note 14.

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*